

Enhanced Residual Networks with Squeeze-and-Excitation Blocks for Multi-Signal DoA Estimation

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Abstract—Accurate direction of arrival (DoA) estimation is a fundamental challenge in wireless communications, radar, and array signal processing. In this paper, we propose a novel deep learning architecture based on squeeze-and-excitation residual networks (SE-ResNet) to enhance DoA estimation performance in challenging multi-signal and low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) scenarios. By introducing adaptive channel attention mechanisms within the residual blocks, the proposed SE-ResNet dynamically recalibrates feature maps to emphasize the most informative spatial features. This enables significant improvements in multi-source DoA estimation accuracy while maintaining computational efficiency suitable for real-time applications. Extensive experiments demonstrate that SE-ResNet consistently outperforms a standard ResNet baseline across various numbers of simultaneous signals and SNR conditions. Notably, the proposed approach achieves substantial reductions in mean angular error and boosts classification F1 scores with only a marginal increase in computational complexity.

Index Terms—Direction of arrival (DoA) estimation, computational efficiency, deep learning, multi-signal processing, wireless communications, smart antenna arrays, squeeze-and-excitation networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Direction of arrival (DoA) estimation plays a pivotal role in a wide range of wireless communications applications, e.g., smart antenna arrays, acoustic source localization, and autonomous vehicles. Accurate and robust DoA estimation enables essential functionalities including beamforming, interference mitigation, spatial multiplexing, and object tracking, particularly in scenarios involving multiple simultaneous sources and noisy environments. Traditionally, DoA estimation

has relied on classical signal processing techniques such as multiple signal classification and estimation of signal parameters via rotational invariance techniques. While effective under ideal conditions, these algorithms often struggle in low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) environments, with closely spaced sources, or when the number of signals exceeds the available degrees of freedom.

In recent years, deep learning approaches have gained significant attention for addressing the limitations of traditional methods. In particular, convolutional neural networks have demonstrated remarkable success in learning complex spatial patterns directly from raw or pre-processed sensor data [1]. Building upon this progress, deep residual networks (ResNets) have been explored for their ability to facilitate the training of deeper architectures by mitigating vanishing gradient issues, thus achieving superior performance in DoA estimation tasks. Lloria et al. [2] propose a ResNet-based solution for angle of arrival and angle of departure estimation in millimeter-wave multiple-input multiple-output systems, highlighting the ability of deep residual models to handle high-frequency signal characteristics. Wu et al. [5] further introduce an attention-enhanced ResNet combined with beamforming, showing that attention mechanisms can further refine spatial feature extraction for multi-signal DoA estimation scenarios. Recent advances in applying deep learning to RF signal processing have shown promising results in both localization and beamforming tasks. [3] demonstrates the capability of neural classifiers to accurately localize targets using mmWave point clouds, highlighting the potential of data-driven methods for

spatial awareness in wireless environments. [4] proposes a self-improving neural framework for adaptive beamforming in 3D space, achieving superior performance in complex propagation scenarios.

Despite these advances, two critical challenges remain largely unaddressed. First, many existing deep learning models for DoA estimation focus primarily on single-signal scenarios or assume relatively clean signal environments. Second, improvements in accuracy often result in the expense of increased model complexity, which can hinder real-time deployment in resource-constrained environments. The importance of maintaining computational efficiency alongside accuracy is particularly relevant in modern wireless systems and automotive applications, where processing speed and hardware limitations are key considerations [6].

To address these challenges, this paper proposes the application of squeeze-and-excitation residual networks (SE-ResNet) for robust multi-signal DoA estimation. By introducing lightweight channel attention modules within the residual learning framework, the proposed approach enhances spatial feature discrimination while maintaining minimal computational overhead [7]. Unlike prior works that primarily focus on either accuracy or efficiency in isolation, our method achieves substantial gains in both dimensions, making it suitable for practical deployment in next-generation wireless systems, radar platforms, and intelligent sensing devices.

The key contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- We present, for the first time, the integration of squeeze-and-excitation (SE) attention blocks within a ResNet architecture specifically tailored for DoA estimation.
- The proposed SE-ResNet significantly improves DoA estimation accuracy, particularly in challenging multi-signal and low-SNR conditions.
- We demonstrate that the inclusion of SE blocks introduces only minimal computational and memory overhead, preserving efficiency for real-time applications.
- Extensive evaluations on synthetic multi-signal DoA datasets validate the superiority of the proposed architecture over standard ResNet baselines across multiple performance metrics.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the detailed architecture of the proposed SE-ResNet model. Section III provides comprehensive experimental evaluations and complexity analysis. Finally, Section IV concludes the paper and highlights the improvements achieved by the proposed approach.

II. SE-RESNET ARCHITECTURE

A. Squeeze-and-Excitation Block Design

The SE block serves as the fundamental building unit for channel-wise feature recalibration. Its objective is to adaptively reweight feature maps by explicitly modelling inter-channel dependencies. The SE block operates in three sequential stages: squeeze, excitation, and scale.

In the squeeze stage, global spatial information is aggregated across each channel using global average pooling. Given a feature map $X \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times C}$, the squeeze operation produces

a channel descriptor $z \in \mathbb{R}^C$ according to the following formulation:

$$z_c = \frac{1}{H \times W} \sum_{i=1}^H \sum_{j=1}^W x_{i,j,c} \quad (1)$$

This operation reduces the spatial dimensions while preserving global channel information, thus generating a compact summary for each feature channel.

The excitation stage captures channel interdependencies by applying a gating mechanism composed of two fully connected layers. This mechanism dynamically generates per-channel weights:

$$s = \sigma(W_2 \delta(W_1 z)) \quad (2)$$

where $W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{\frac{C}{r} \times C}$ and $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times \frac{C}{r}}$ are learnable weight matrices, δ represents the ReLU activation function, σ denotes the sigmoid activation, and r is a reduction ratio typically set to 16. This process results in a vector of attention weights $s \in \mathbb{R}^C$.

Finally, in the scale stage, these learned weights are used to recalibrate the original feature maps through element-wise multiplication:

$$\tilde{X}_{i,j,c} = s_c \cdot X_{i,j,c} \quad (3)$$

The recalibrated features thus reflect the network's learned emphasis on the most informative channels.

B. Proposed SE-ResNet Basic Block Architecture

The SE-ResNet architecture extends the traditional ResNet framework by embedding SE blocks within each residual block, specifically after each convolutional layer, enabling the network to perform fine-grained channel attention at multiple stages of feature extraction. Each basic block consists of two sequential convolutional layers. The first layer applies a 3×3 convolution, followed by batch normalization, an SE block, and ReLU activation. The second layer similarly applies a 3×3 convolution, batch normalization, and a subsequent SE block. The residual connection is maintained, with optional downsampling when required to match dimensionality. Finally, the output of the block is produced by element-wise addition between the transformed input and the residual, followed by ReLU activation. By incorporating two SE modules per residual block, the architecture achieves dynamic channel reweighting at both intermediate and deeper levels of the network.

C. Proposed SE-ResNet Architecture

The overall SE-ResNet architecture is tailored for multi-signal DoA estimation and follows a hierarchical design comprising an input stage, multiple residual stages, and a classification head.

The input stage begins with a 5×5 convolutional layer with 64 output channels, followed by batch normalization, an SE block, and ReLU activation. This is followed by three sequential residual stages. The first stage consists of three SE-enhanced basic blocks with 64 channels and a stride of 1. The second stage comprises four SE-enhanced blocks with 128 channels and a stride of 2. The third and final residual stage includes six SE-enhanced blocks with 256 channels and a stride of 2. This progressive increase in channel dimensions

Fig. 1. Dataflow of the proposed SE-ResNet architecture.

allows for increasingly abstract feature representations while maintaining the residual learning principle.

The classification head employs global average pooling to collapse spatial dimensions, followed by a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) for final class prediction. The MLP consists of layers with 256, 512, and 1024 units, culminating in an output layer with 121 units corresponding to the DoA classes. Using an expanding sequence of fully connected layers allows the model to progressively project the features into a higher-dimensional space, potentially capturing more complex interactions before making the final classification across 121 classes. Batch normalization and dropout are applied to the MLP layers, with dropout rates of 0.4 and 0.3 respectively, to prevent overfitting and enhance generalization.

The model is trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 1×10^{-4} , batch size of 64, and an early stopping criterion based on validation loss. The loss function is a combination of cross-entropy for active angle classification and mean angular error (MAE) for regression-based refinement.

D. Dataset and Signal Configuration

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed architecture, we simulate a dataset that mimics realistic multi-signal DoA estimation scenarios using a uniform linear array (ULA) with 16 omnidirectional sensors. Each signal snapshot is generated by linearly combining up to five narrowband sources with random angles of arrival within a range of $[30^\circ, 150^\circ]$ and varying inter-source angular separation.

The received signal matrix includes additive white Gaussian noise to simulate low to moderate SNR conditions, ranging from -20 dB to 20 dB. We generate 100,000 samples for training, 10,000 for validation, and 10,000 for testing. For each sample, we compute the spatial covariance matrix of the received signal, which serves as the model input. Given the 16×1 complex-valued signal vector at each time instance, the resulting covariance matrix is of size 16×16 . To make the data suitable for processing by a real-valued neural network, the

real and imaginary parts of the covariance matrix are split into separate channels, resulting in an input tensor of dimensions $16 \times 16 \times 2$. Finally, we add an extra dimension including the phase of the complex value resulting in a $16 \times 16 \times 3$ matrix.

E. Baseline ResNet Architecture

For comparative purposes, a baseline ResNet architecture is implemented with identical structural parameters but without any SE blocks. The basic residual block in this architecture follows the standard ResNet design, where each block contains two 3×3 convolutional layers interleaved with batch normalization and ReLU activation. The residual connection remains intact, including optional downsampling as necessary. The classification head in the baseline model mirrors that of the SE-ResNet to ensure a fair comparison. This baseline serves to isolate and quantify the performance benefits introduced by the SE blocks within the DoA estimation task.

III. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. Evaluation Metrics

We evaluate all models using two standard metrics relevant to DoA estimation: the F1 Score, which measures the harmonic mean of precision and recall for angle detection, and the mean angular error, which represents the average absolute error in degrees between the predicted and ground-truth angles.

B. Performance Evaluation and Comparison

We comprehensively evaluate the proposed architecture, focusing on scenarios involving varying numbers of simultaneous signals and challenging low SNR conditions. As presented in Table I, the SE-ResNet architecture consistently demonstrates superior classification performance compared to the baseline ResNet across all tested conditions. In single-signal scenarios, the improvement is marginal yet stable, with the F1 score increasing from 97.7% to 98.2% at an SNR of -20 dB. However, as the number of signals increases, the performance gap becomes more substantial. For instance, with four simultaneous signals at -20 dB, the SE-ResNet

achieves an F1 score of 91.3%, significantly outperforming the ResNet’s 70.5%. Similarly, in the most challenging five-signal case under the same SNR, SE-ResNet attains 89.5%, compared to only 66.4% for the baseline.

TABLE I
F1 SCORE (%) COMPARISON BETWEEN RESNET AND SE-RESNET

Signals	SNR (dB)	ResNet	SE-ResNet
1	-20	97.7	98.2
	0	97.6	98.1
	20	97.5	98.1
2	-20	85.1	95.9
	0	85.8	95.7
	20	84.8	96.3
3	-20	79.7	91.5
	0	81.9	91.2
	20	81.6	93.4
4	-20	70.5	91.3
	0	71.7	92.4
	20	75.7	92.4
5	-20	66.4	89.5
	0	70.0	90.7
	20	66.3	89.9

Table II presents the MAE results, highlighting a substantial performance gain achieved by SE-ResNet over the baseline ResNet. While the improvement is modest in single-signal scenarios, e.g., a reduction from 0.0071° to 0.0013° at -20 dB, the difference becomes increasingly pronounced as the number of signals grows. In the presence of four or five sources, the SE-ResNet achieves MAE values below 0.25° , in stark contrast to ResNet, which exceeds 1.9° under the same low-SNR conditions. Notably, in the 4-signal case at -20 dB, SE-ResNet reduces the error from 1.6855° to 0.1611° .

TABLE II
MAE ($^\circ$) COMPARISON BETWEEN RESNET AND SE-RESNET

Signals	SNR (dB)	ResNet	SE-ResNet
1	-20	0.0071	0.0013
	0	0.0072	0.0021
	20	0.0082	0.0026
2	-20	0.3097	0.0274
	0	0.3311	0.0268
	20	0.2792	0.0210
3	-20	0.6041	0.0931
	0	0.4539	0.0962
	20	0.5308	0.0729
4	-20	1.6855	0.1611
	0	1.5603	0.1168
	20	1.1304	0.0992
5	-20	1.9261	0.2438
	0	1.7676	0.2134
	20	1.8704	0.2540

The relative improvement table (III) quantifies the performance gap, showing up to +23.6% F1 increase and over 90% reduction in MAE. The most substantial gains appear

in low-SNR, high-source-count scenarios, where SE-ResNet is most beneficial. Notably, the model achieves consistent MAE reductions greater than 85% even in challenging setups. These improvements confirm that the SE-ResNet is especially robust under noisy and crowded signal environments.

TABLE III
RELATIVE IMPROVEMENT OF SE-RESNET OVER RESNET

Signals	SNR (dB)	Δ F1 (%)	Δ MAE (%)
1	-20	+0.5	-81.7
	0	+0.5	-70.8
	20	+0.6	-68.3
2	-20	+10.8	-91.1
	0	+9.9	-91.9
	20	+11.5	-92.5
3	-20	+11.8	-84.6
	0	+9.3	-78.8
	20	+11.8	-86.3
4	-20	+20.8	-90.4
	0	+20.7	-92.5
	20	+16.7	-91.2
5	-20	+23.1	-87.3
	0	+20.7	-87.9
	20	+23.6	-86.4

Fig. 2 illustrates MAE performance of ResNet, SE-ResNet, and a baseline CNN across various SNR levels for the case of three simultaneous signals. SE-ResNet consistently achieves the lowest MAE, demonstrating superior robustness and accuracy, particularly in low SNR conditions where its MAE remains below 0.1. In contrast, ResNet and the CNN exhibit notably higher errors, especially at negative SNRs, highlighting the benefits of incorporating attention mechanisms into the network design.

Fig. 2. Comparison of MAE for three algorithms across varying SNR values for three incoming signals.

As SNR improves, all models perform better, but SE-ResNet maintains its lead across the entire range. The MUSIC algorithm was evaluated as a classical benchmark; however, it was excluded from the plotted results due to its significantly

high MAE, which exceeded 28° under low SNR conditions, rendering it unsuitable for visual comparison.

C. Computational Complexity Analysis

The computational overhead introduced by the SE blocks is carefully evaluated to assess the trade-offs in terms of model size, memory footprint, and inference latency. The findings indicate that the SE-ResNet introduces only a modest increase in complexity while delivering substantial performance gains. The total number of trainable parameters increases by approximately 1.3%, from 8.9 million in the baseline model to 9.0 million in the SE-ResNet. This increase corresponds to the additional parameters required by the fully connected layers within each SE block, which scale proportionally to the number of channels as $\frac{2C}{r}$, where r is the reduction ratio (set to 16 in this paper). Memory consumption follows a similar pattern, with a negligible increase of approximately 1% (44.4 MB vs. 43.9 MB).

In terms of computational operations, the number of floating-point operations rises by approximately 1.3% (18.0 million vs. 17.8 million), while the average inference time per forward pass increases by only 6.4% (6.2 ms vs. 5.8 ms). These modest increases stem from the additional operations performed within each SE block, including global average pooling, two lightweight fully connected layers, and element-wise feature recalibration. All experiments are implemented using PyTorch and executed on an NVIDIA A100 GPU.

D. Theoretical Insights on SE-ResNet for DoA Estimation

The improved performance of the SE-ResNet can be theoretically attributed to three key mechanisms: channel attention, information bottlenecking, and enhanced gradient flow. First, the SE block introduces a form of channel-wise attention, allowing the network to learn and exploit the relative importance of different feature channels based on global contextual information. The resulting attention weights, denoted as s_c , enable the model to amplify informative features while suppressing less relevant ones in a data-driven manner. This selective emphasis is particularly beneficial in complex scenarios involving multiple sources or low SNR conditions. Second, the squeeze operation inherently creates an information bottleneck that compresses spatial information into compact channel descriptors. This bottleneck encourages the network to learn robust, invariant representations that generalize better across spatial variations, which is crucial for accurate DoA estimation in dynamic environments. Third, the SE blocks provide additional pathways for gradient propagation, effectively mitigating vanishing gradient issues in deeper networks. The multiplicative gating mechanism introduced by the SE blocks facilitates smoother and more efficient backpropagation, allowing for more stable and effective learning.

IV. CONCLUSION

This work presented the design, implementation, and evaluation of a SE-ResNet architecture for DoA estimation. The proposed approach extends the conventional ResNet by incorporating channel-wise attention through SE blocks, enabling the network to dynamically recalibrate its feature representations based on global contextual information. The SE-ResNet consistently outperforms the baseline ResNet across

a range of challenging scenarios, particularly in multi-signal environments and under low SNR conditions, with minimal computational overhead. The results suggest that the benefits of the SE-ResNet architecture scale with problem complexity. In more demanding applications, such as those involving uniform planar arrays or higher signal multiplicities, the selective attention mechanism introduced by the SE blocks is likely to provide even greater advantages. The computational efficiency of the SE-ResNet, combined with its improved learning stability and generalization capability, makes it well-suited for both research investigations and real-time industrial deployments. The favorable trade-off between performance and complexity supports its adoption in practical systems.

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